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Communicative Competencies in English of Grade Seven Students at Concord Integrated School

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to determine the communicative competencies in English of Grade 12 students at Concord Integrated School. The researcher employed the correlational survey method where the profile of the students in terms of the language/dialect spoken at home, attitude towards learning English and the degree of influence of multimedia resources are obtained through survey questionnaires. The level of students' communicative competencies in English are obtained through the midyear achievement test and the level of teachers' communicative competencies in English are obtained through the communicative competency test for teachers. The study revealed that the level of Grade Seven students' communicative competencies in English at Concord Integrated High School is average and is influenced by their attitude towards learning English, exposure to multimedia resources and teachers' communicative competencies in English while their language first dialect spoken at home had no effect on them.

Keywords: *communicative competencies, english language, grade seven*

Introduction

Communicative competence allows people of all different levels linguistically to speak to each other. It similarly allows for more positive interactions amongst one another. This is considered one of the indicators of a student's success. Communicating effectively in a language requires the speaker's good understanding of linguistic, sociolinguistic and socio-cultural aspects of that language. This understanding will enable him to use the right language in the right context for the right purpose and then he can be referred to as communicatively competent. However, the realization of this level of knowledge and understanding is always a challenge for Filipino language learners. They often struggle through their journey towards the achievement of this goal and are often met with many obstacles. Therefore, many arguments have been raised against designing language courses and programs for Filipino language contexts to achieve this goal. The term 'communicative competence' was first introduced by Hymes in (1972) as a sociolinguistic concept in reaction to the concept of 'linguistic competence' which was proposed by Chomsky in 1965. Chomsky's concept was "concerned with the tacit knowledge of language structure" but "omits almost everything of socio-cultural, significance" (Hymes, 1972: 270- 280).

Educators and even leaders are alarmed by the seeming retrogression of the youth and the students in the learning of the language. Many teacher laments or bewail the inability of their students to communicate effectively in English. Educators and even administrators are concerned with the negative turn of events.

Studies and observation show that the communicative competencies of the students have deteriorated. The students nowadays could hardly express their thoughts in simple language and much difficulty in giving meanings from the printed materials and in writing compositions of related sentences.

Since formal education is the best vehicle for language learning, it is not surprising why the school is the easy suspect for the problem. If learning takes place in school, as indeed it does, the English instruction should be improved.

Many factors could be cited for the deterioration of English in the country taking most of the blame in school. Some probable causes of this alarming deterioration in the quality of English are language/dialect spoken at home, attitude, towards learning English, teachers' communicative competencies in English and influence of multimedia resources.

English is one of the core subjects in the elementary. Yet for all its importance, English teachers have been plagued by a great number of obstacles in their attempt to create an ideal communicative learning situation inside the classrooms. English, as a Second language, requires a good deal of mastery before it can be used adequately by the learner. This suggests that the teachers, parents and school officials should be aware of the student's strengths and weaknesses so as to avoid activities that may prove to be hindrance in language learning in the classroom.

The identification of the strengths and weaknesses as well as problems and deficiencies constitute one of the basic functions of the educative process. It allows for the objective evaluation of learning gains as well as the identification of answers where difficulties or obstacles are present.

To do this however, it is necessary to select a school unit wherein all aspects of the problem can be considered and an in-depth analysis can be made, using all the resources and instruments of research available. English is one of the core subjects in the elementary. Yet for all its importance, English teachers have been plagued by a great number of obstacles in their attempt to create an ideal communicative learning situation inside the classrooms. English, as a Second language, requires a good deal of mastery before it can be used adequately by the learner. This suggests that the teachers, parents and school officials should be aware of the student's strengths and weaknesses so as to avoid activities that may prove to be hindrance in language learning in the classroom.

The researcher, being an English teacher deemed it wise to find out the level of communicative camera-notes of the grade seven students and its relationship to some selected variables at Concord Integrated School Hence, the study was conceived.

Research Questions

To furtherly have an in-depth investigation, the main objective of this study is to determine the communicative competencies in English of Grade 12 students at Concord Integrated School. It also sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents with regards to:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. educational attainment
2. What is the level of students' communicative competencies in English along the following parameters:
 - 2.1. speaking skills;
 - 2.2. reading skills; and
 - 2.3. writing skills?
3. What is the level of teachers' communicative competencies in English?
4. What is the degree of influence of multimedia resources on the communicative competencies of the subject students?
5. Based on the study's findings, what is the significant difference among the communicative skills of the subject students?

Methodology

Research Design

Sevilla et al. (2012) asserted that correlational study is a type of descriptive research which is designed to help determine the extent to which the different variables are related to each other in the population of interest.

In this study the researcher employed the correlational survey method where the profile of the students in terms or the language/dialect spoken at home, attitude towards learning English and the degree of influence of multimedia resources are obtain through survey questionnaires. The level of students' communicative competencies in English are obtain through the midyear achievement test and the level of teachers' communicative competencies in English are obtain through the communicative competency test for teachers. After the data gathering, the researcher will tabulate, analyze, classify and more importantly, will establish the prevalent relationships among the existing variables.

Moreover, the researcher believes that this kind of design is aligned on the objectives of this study as it aimed to determine the communicative competencies in English of Grade Seven students at Concord Integrated School on selected variables, school year 2022-2023.

Respondents

At Concord Integrated School, there are 211 Grade Seven, 5 sections. There are 5 English teachers each handling 1 classes. All classes are group heterogeneously. A total of 211 students or 5 sections will be chosen, one section each under the 5 English teachers will comprise the population of the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Grade and Section</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
VII- Banaba	22	21	43
VII – Ipil-Ipil	23	20	43
VII – Lawaan	19	22	41
VII – Narra	20	22	42
VII – Yakal	21	21	42
Total	105	106	211

Instrument

The instruments used in the study included the midyear achievement test, questionnaires and the Regional Proficiency Test in English for Elementary Teachers.

Midyear Achievement Tests is used to determine the level of communicative competencies of the grade seven students, the scope has been based on the English Learning Competencies (ELC). This was obtained from the results of their midyear achievement test.

The Proficiency Test in English for Secondary Teachers is a Regional Test in English in Region VIII for teachers which the researcher have secured from the division office.

The researcher used the same basis of interpretation to determine the level of communicative competencies of the students and the teachers' communicative competencies in English. These are quantified in table 2.

Table 2. *Midyear Achievement Test and Proficiency Test for Teachers in English*

<i>Percent of Scores (%)</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
70 and above	Superior
58-69	Above average
46-57	Average
34-45	Below Average
33 and below	Poor

The researcher prepared a set of questionnaires used in this study. The set of questionnaires were for the student participant. It composed of questions that would gather the student-related variables such as language/dialect spoken at home and attitude toward learning English and the degree of influence of multimedia resources to the communicative competencies in English of the students.

The reliability and validity of the questions, the researcher submitted the questionnaire to three validators. The expertise of the school's Master Teacher of English Grade Seven, Division Education Program Supervisor in English, and an expert in correlational studies which type of descriptive research, to assess the content and to contribute to the further development of the researcher-made interview questions.

Procedure

The researcher commenced with relevant readings in the school library and trusted online websites to further understand the chosen topic through its existing literature and potential gaps. Eventually, the working title and the study's objectives were crafted, followed by the appropriate design and data analysis methods.

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division of Hinabangan, Western Samar through its Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and the research locale's principal of Concord Integrated School requested through written letters sent to ask approval of the research proposal. Time schedule was set by the Principal in answering the questionnaire, the researcher guaranteed that the atmosphere kept non-threatening, friendly, and bias-free.

To avoid class interruptions, the study has been conducted in a natural class activity during the class period in English and is personally administered by the researcher. They were given 30 minutes to finish answering the questionnaires. The level of Communicative Competencies of the students will be taken from the results of the midyear achievement test.

The communicative competency test in English for the teachers were accomplished and retrieved on the same day. The participants were aware of the importance of their honest answers and of the confidentiality of their answers to ensure the objectivity of the results.

The researcher interpreted the meanings of each significant response as assured to adhere to the research protocols to guarantee the original description manifested in the interpretive meanings. The interpreted meanings arranged into clusters which paved the way for themes to emerge. In addition, these themes would be integrated into a detailed description of the overall essence of the experience. The step aided by exploring the codes' interrelationships and consistencies and referencing the stated literature in an earlier chapter of this study. Also, the writing has been cited notable quotations from the interview transcripts to underscore the most important themes within the findings and possible oppositions. Lastly, the questionnaire that have been answered, all tests tallied, organized and classified.

Data Analysis

The researcher employed the following Statistical instruments in this study; frequency count; percentage; arithmetic mean; standard deviation; Friedman One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the Chi-Square to present the pertinent information to be gathered, to answer the problems and to test the hypotheses to be formulated.

Frequency Count and Percentage, these two descriptive measures used in determining the profile of the respondents in terms of selected personal variables like language/dialect spoken at home and attitude towards learning English.

To identify the level of communicative competencies of the Grade Seven Pupils and the teachers' communicative competencies in English with respect to reading, speaking and writing skills Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviation used in this study.

In order to ascertain the significant difference among the communicative skills of the subject students, Friedman One-way Analysis of Variance used to this study.

Chi-Square employed to determine the magnitude of significant relationship between some selected variables and the students' level of communicative competencies in English.

Ethical Considerations

All possible corrections and suggestions by the validators shall be considered and followed to ensure that the data gathering adhere to protocol and school rules on child protection, education standards, and research ethics.

Moreover, the confidentiality of the participants is guaranteed by the researcher. Responses are kept confidential in order to ensure that the researcher comply with Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act.

In addition to this, the researcher will comply the standards for ethical research such as the knowledge, truth and error avoidance. This feature has been possible for the researcher to refrain from inventing, manipulating, or distorting study findings in order to support the truth and reduce mistakes. Furthermore, the preferences of many respondents within the organizations shall be respected.

Consequently, the participants in this study were not required to provide their names or identities during the data collection, analysis, and reporting of the study findings within the research questionnaire in order to ensure their confidentiality. The researcher shall also obtain the consent of every respondent who take part in the study. The study's objective was made clear to the respondents, who are inform that the data they will be provided would only be used for research.

Results and Discussion

Level of Students' Communicative Competencies in English

Exhibited in table 3 are the data on the students' level of communicative competencies in English.

Table 3. Level of Students' Communicative Competencies in English

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Level of Communication Competencies</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Reading	59.38	Above Average
Speaking	44.55	Below Average
Writing	49.81	Average
Overall	51.54	Average

The level of Students' Communicative Competencies in English was based on the results of their midyear achievement test. Table 3 presented the level of the students' communicative competencies along the three parameters namely, reading, speaking and writing.

The table revealed that the students garnered a mean of 59.38 or above average in their reading competency level, 44.55 or below average in their speaking competency level and 49.81 or average in their writing competency level. The table also showed that the overall mean of the students is 51.54 or average in their level of communicative competencies in English.

It can be deduced that the students mastered most of the skills they learned in reading or are good in reading, and they encountered difficulty in mastering the skills in speaking.

Profile of the Grade 7 Students

Language/Dialect Spoken at Home. Table 6 displays the data concerning the language spoken at home by the students.

Table 4. Language/ Dialect Spoken at Home

<i>Language/Dialect Spoken at Home</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Filipino	177	84
Visaya	13	6
Pampanga	10	5
Pangasinense	4	3
Other Dialects	3	1.5
English	3	1.5
Total	211	100%

A cursory examination of Table 4 revealed that 177 or 84 percent speak Filipino, 13 or 6 percent Visaya, 10 or 5 percent speaks Pampango, 7 or 3 percent speak Pangasinense, 3 or 1.5 percent speaks English at home other dialects and only one or 0.5 percent speaks English at home. As already pointed out, majority of the students speak Filipino.

Attitude towards learning English

Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents on attitude towards learning English.

Table 5. Showing the Attitude of the Students towards Learning English

<i>Attitude</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Very Desirable	31	15
Desirable	163	77
Less Desirable	17	8
Total	211	100%

As presented in Table 7, thirty one (31) or 15 percent possess a very desirable attitude towards learning English, one hundred sixty three (163) or 77 percent have desirable attitude and seventeen 17 or 8 percent have less desirable attitude towards learning English. It can be deduced from the above findings that majority of the students have desirable attitude towards learning English.

Level of Teachers’ Communicative Competencies in English

Table 6 the level of teachers’ communicative competencies in English based on their proficiency test in English.

Table 6. *Level of Teacher’s Communicative Competencies in English*

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Level of Communicative Competency</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Reading	68.00	Above Average
Speaking	49.00	Average
Writing	58.00	Above Average
Overall	58.40	Above Average

Close scrutiny of the table showed that the teachers generated a mean of 68.00 or above average in their reading competency level in English, 49.00 or average in their speaking competency level and 58.00 or above average in their uniting competency level. As gleaned from the table, the teacher’s overall mean of 58.40 or above average in their communicative competencies in English was derived. This implies that the English teachers are highly competent in their communicative competencies in their communicative competencies in English.

Degree of Influence of Multimedia Resources

The data on the profile of the students on the influence of the multimedia resources to the communicative competencies of the subject students are presented in the table.

Table 7. *Degree of Influence of Multimedia Resources on the Students’ Communicative Competencies in English*

<i>Degree of Influence</i>	<i>Audio Visual Media</i>		<i>Print Media</i>		<i>Modern Technology</i>	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Very High	127	60	17	8	0	0
High	73	34	152	72	15	7
Moderate	11	6	30	14	54	26
Low	0	0	12	6	98	46
Not At all	0	0	0	0	44	21
Total	211	100%	211	100%	211	100%

It can be noted in Table 7 that 127, or 60 percent are very highly influenced by the audio-visual media in their communicative competencies in English, 73, or 34 percent are highly influenced 11, or 6 percent are moderately influenced, nobody is low and not influenced at all.

The table also reflected that 17, or 18 percent are very highly influenced by print media in their communicative competencies, 152, or 72 percent are highly influences, 30, or 14 percent are moderately influenced, 12, or 6 percent are low, and nobody are not influenced at all.

As gleaned from the data, nobody is very highly influenced by modern technology in their communicative competencies in English, 15, or 7 percent are highly influenced, 54, or 26 percent are moderately influenced, 98, or 36 percent have a very low influence and 44, or 21 percent are not influenced at all.

Based on the findings, it was concluded that the majority of the students are very highly influenced by the audio-visual media. Generally, the data showed that the students’ communicative competencies are highly influenced by the multimedia resources.

Results of the Analysis of Variance among the three Communicative Skills.

Table 10 shows the result of the analysis of variance among the three communicative skills.

Table 8. *Results of the Analysis of Variance among the Three Communicative Skills*

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>Significance</i>
Between Groups	866.7	2	433.35	F = 13.28	Significant
Within Groups	391.7	12	31.64		
Total	1258.4	14			

The computed value of 13.28 at 2 and 12 degrees of freedom is greater than the critical values, which are 3.88 at 0.05 and 6.93 at 0.01 levels of significance. Hence, a substantial proof was found to refute the null hypothesis. This implies that there is a significant difference among the Communicative skills in English of the Grade Seven students.

Close scrutiny at the table shows the significant difference between the reading and speaking skills, as revealed b the t-valve which is 9.789 that is greater than the critical value of 1.960 at 0.05 and 2.576 at .01 level of significance.

Extent of Relationship between the Students' Communicative Competencies and their Attitude towards Learning English

Table 11 reveals the extent of relationship between the communicative competencies in English and attitude towards learning English of the students.

Table 11. *Extent of Relationship between the Students' Communicative Competencies and their Attitude towards Learning English*

Communicative Competency Level	Attitude Towards learning English						Total
	Very Desirable		Desirable		Less Desirable		
	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Superior	18	13	17	25	5	1.3	40
Above Average	24	12	7	20	1	1.1	32
Average	27	20	31	37	1	2.0	59
Below Average	2	15	44	29	0	1.5	46
Poor	0	11	34	22	0	1.1	34
Total	71	71	133	133	7	7	211

Table 11 presents the analysis on the relationship between the students' communicative competencies in English and their attitude towards learning English. The computed value between them was 79.53 utilizing 9 degrees of freedom. The computed chi-square is greater than the critical value of 15.51 at .05 and 20.09 at .01 levels of significance.

This guarantees that there is significant relationship that exists between the students' communicative competencies and their attitude towards learning English.

Yen (2010) stated that attitude is an important factor in upgrading communication skills in English both as a language and as a subject. The students have desirable attitude and an average and an average level in their communicative competencies in English.

The study of Obcena (2011) has the same result that attitude or interest to learn English positively predicted communicative competencies. Desirable attitudes also show significant relationship on the students' average level of communicative competencies in English.

Extent of Relationship between Students' and Teachers' Communicative Competencies in English

Table 12 exhibits the extent of relationship between the students' and teachers' communicative competencies in English.

Table 12. *Extent of Relationship between Students' and Teachers' Communicative Competencies in English*

Parameter	Pupil		Teacher	
	O	E	O	E
Reading	59.38	63.69	68.00	63.69
Speaking	44.55	46.78	49.00	46.78
Writing	49.81	53.90	58.00	53.90

The computed value of chi-square, 9.02 at 2 degrees of freedom is greater than its critical value of 5.99 at 0.05 and less than the critical value 9.21 at 0.01 level of significance, thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the students' and the teachers' communicative competencies at .05 but not at .01 level of significance. This means that the teachers' communicative competencies in English influenced the students' communicative competencies in English. This goes to show that the teacher is a great factor to influence the students' communicative competencies in English.

This is confirmed by Florendo (2010) who believed that the responsibility for the improvement of students in language rests to some extent on every teacher. The quality teaching may be gauged by the quality of learning on the part of the students. The simple language error in the language seems indicative of poor teaching to which students have been subjected to. Pulilias (2013) also stated that the teacher is many persons. The teacher is "learned" ---he should know more than his students.

This is also supported by the study of Grambs (2012), which revealed that the communicative competencies of the teachers have a great influence on the students' communicative competencies in English.

Extent of Relationship between Students' Communicative Competencies in English and the Influence of Multimedia Resources

Table 13 exhibits the extent at relationship between the students' communicative competencies in English and the influence of the Multimedia Resources in their communicative competencies in English.

This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there existed a significant relationship between the students' communicative competencies in English and the influence of multimedia resources at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the multimedia resources influence the communicative competencies of the students.

Table 13. *Extent of Relationship between Students' Communicative Competencies in English and the Influence of Multimedia Resources*

Communicative Competency	Influence Very High	High		Medium		Low		Not at All		Total	
		O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E		
		Superior	12	9	19	15	5	6	3		7
Above Average	10	7	12	12	6	5	3	5	1	2	32
Average	16	14	24	23	9	9	9	10	1	4	59
Below Average	7	11	22	17	8	7	5	8	4	3	46
Poor	4	8	3	13	4	5	16	6	7	2	34
TOTAL	49	49	80	80	32	32	36	36	14	14	211

This confirms the study of Christmann and Badgett (Edwin, Christmann@sru.edu) those Students who were supplemented with computer assisted instructions and other modern technology attained higher academic achievement than those receiving only traditional instructions.

The study confirms also the study of Espaldon (2010) that exposure to multimedia has a positive influence on the communicative competencies of the students.

Summary on the Extent of Relationship between the Pupils' Communicative Competencies and the Selected Variables

Table 14 shows the summary on the extent of relationship between the students' communicative competencies and the selected variables.

Table 14. *Summary of Chi-square Test on the Extent of Relationship between the Students' Communicative Competencies and Selected Variables*

Variables	Compound Value	df	Critical Value	Findings
Language/Dialect Spoken at Home	19.63	20	0.05=31.41 0.01=37.57	Not Significant
Attitude towards Learning English	79.53	8	0.05=15.51 0.01=20.09	Significant at 0.01
Teachers' Communicative Competencies in English	9.02	2	0.05=5.99 0.01=9.21	Significant at 0.05
Influence of Multimedia Resources	52.02	16	0.05=26.30 0.01=32.00	Significant at 0.01

The students' communicative competencies in English, their attitude towards learning English and the influence of the multimedia resources are significantly related at 0.01 level of significance and the teachers' level of communicative competencies at .05 level of significance. Their language/dialect spoken at home has no significant relationship to their communicative competencies in English. This means that the students' level of communicative competencies in English is greatly influenced by their attitude towards learning English, the teachers' communicative competencies in English and the influence of multimedia resources. Their language dialects spoken at home have no influence at all.

Conclusions

The level of Grade Seven students' communicative competencies in English at Concord Integrated High School is average and is influenced by their attitude towards learning English, exposure to multimedia resources and teachers' communicative competencies in English while their language first dialect spoken at home had no effect on them.

On account of the significant findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

To improve students' communicative competencies in English in the grade level, teachers should encourage the students to speak English inside the classroom more importantly during class discussions.

Further guidance and motivation should be given to students to attain desirable attitude towards learning English.

Teachers should apply different strategies in teaching the language so that the learning could adopt the higher order thinking skills (HOTS) in their discussions which will help the children think critically and eventually express themselves freely and fluently in English.

Teachers should speak the English language during conversations inside and outside the classroom to improve their communicative competencies in English.

Since the multimedia resources are the “in-thing” of today’s generation, teachers have to optimize the use of those modern resources for classroom use and individual instruction. Teachers should utilize the media that is frequently used by students especially the resources that require the optimum use of speaking, reading and writing.

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